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Target indicator quality in CMEMS MFCs

Deliverable Contributors:	Name	Organisation	Role / Title
Deliverable Leader	Skakala J	PML	WP6 leader
Contributing Author(s)	Wakamatsu T	NERSC	Contributor
	Bertino L	NERSC	Contributor
	Teruzzi A	OGS	Contributor
	Lazzari P	OGS	Contributor
	Alvarez E	OGS	Contributor
	Cossarini G	OGS	Contributor
	Spada S	OGS	Contributor
	Nerger L	AWI	Contributor
	Vliegen S	AWI	Contributor
	Brankart JM	UGA	Contributor
	Brasseur P	UGA	Contributor
Reviewer(s)	Ciavatta S	MOi	Advisory board
Final review and approval	Skakala J	PML	Project Coordinator

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1. Scope

The focus of WP6 is improving the biogeochemical model parametrization, which is part of SEAMLESS ambition to better simulate the SEAMLESS target ecosystem indicators on the CMEMS MFC domains. The improved parametrization was delivered in WP6.1 and followed in WP6.2 by the final assessment of the SEAMLESS developments from WP3-WP6.1. Finally, in WP6.3 we used the best performing SEAMLESS systems, evaluated in WP6.2, to deliver the final SEAMLESS target indicator 1-year reanalyses on the CMEMS MFC domains (North Atlantic, Arctic, North-West European Shelf, Mediterranean and Baltic domain).

This document aims at (i) introducing the final, best performing, SEAMLESS model configurations including their validation, (ii) discussing the final reanalyses of SEAMLESS ecosystem target indicators (from WP6.3) using the best performing SEAMLESS model configurations and (iii) most importantly providing final guidelines to CMEMS about production and characteristics of these products.

This report synthesizes the SEAMLESS work from WP3-WP6 that has been largely reported in D3.2 (Ciavatta et al, 2022), D3.4 (Brasseur et al, 2022), D.4.1 (Nerger et al, 2023), D4.2 (Bertino et al, 2023) and D5.1 (Cossarini et al, 2023), adding the developments from WP6.

2. Introduction

Marine biogeochemistry models have easily hundreds of relatively poorly constrained parameters, which are often tuned to give optimal model performance as evaluated by the observations. Strictly speaking such tuning is required after each model development, since the parameter values often hide substantial error compensations in the model. SEAMLESS developed in WP2 and WP3 ensemble methods for both 1D and 3D applications across five CMEMS MFC models and domains. These methods are extremely well suited for model calibration of the relevant CMEMS MFC models. More than that, the complex parameter 1D sensitivity analysis performed in task 2 of WP3 of SEAMLESS, allowed us to select the most relevant parameters that need to be calibrated to optimally estimate the SEAMLESS ecosystem target indicators. Furthermore, in WP2 a joint parameter-state estimation capability was developed in EAT software, allowing us to estimate parameters in 1D dynamically (as time-varying) across the assimilation period.

The role of WP6 is to utilize these results and improve the estimates of SEAMLESS target indicators through better parametrizations of CMEMS MFC models. This enables us to produce higher quality target indicator products delivered to CMEMS. Most of the SEAMLESS partners performed in task 6.1 1D calibrations of the most sensitive parameters from SEAMLESS D3.2 report, selecting the optimal parameter values. These have been then evaluated in the 3D environment by the series of free model simulations and the model performance was compared to the previous model parametrization. IGE and NERSC have used DA schemes estimating parameters dynamically in time (both) and space (only IGE), and validated the parameter-estimating scheme comparing the

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performance of different ensemble sizes at different lead times (IGE), or with the set-up using constant parameter values (NERSC). The optimal model and assimilation set-ups based on SEAMLESS developments were subsequently selected for all MFC systems, and are presented together with their validation in Section (3). These assimilation systems from Section (3) are recommended to be implemented operationally by the CMEMS MFCs. In Section (4) we discuss new reanalyses of the SEAMLESS ecosystem target indicators based on those newly developed ensemble assimilation systems. These indicators correspond to either existing CMEMS portfolio, or are entirely new products suggested to be included in the CMEMS portfolio. In Section (5) we summarize all the final recommendations of the SEAMLESS consortium to CMEMS on the implementation and delivery of the SEAMLESS developments/products across all the MFCs.

3. The best performing systems on MFC domains

In this section we summarize the final configurations for the MFC systems across the five CMEMS MFC domains, to be recommended to CMEMS for future operational implementation. These configurations are based on pre-SEAMLESS systems and include the developments from SEAMLESS WP3-WP6 that have been demonstrated to improve the MFC system skill. The developments were (i) introducing the ensemble capability and ensemble-based DA into the MFC systems (WP3), (ii) improving the coupling between physics and biogeochemistry within the DA (WP4), (iii) improving the capacity to assimilate data from multiple observing platforms (WP5) and (iv) improving the biogeochemistry model parametrization (WP6, task 1). The recommended developments will be summarized across the five MFC domains, each SEAMLESS partner providing a section describing the selected updates. The developments from WP3-WP5 have been already described in detail and validated in previous SEAMLESS deliverables from WP3-WP5, here we will additionally provide validation for the choice of model parametrization, developed often through joint parameter-state estimation experiments in 1D models run at different sites (task 1 of SEAMLESS WP6), using configurations and software developments from SEAMLESS WP2.

3.1 The system in the BAL MFC domain

3.1.1 The R&D system set-up

Following the 3D data assimilation experiments documented in deliverable 4.1 and 4.2, AWI has chosen the following (best performing) configuration to represent SEAMLESS target indicators in the Baltic MFC domain: (i) AWI used the ensemble system from WP4, (ii) both satellite sea surface and chlorophyll data were assimilated, (iii) chlorophyll observations were assimilated weakly-coupled (updating only the BGC variables) while the sea surface temperature (SST) observations were assimilated strongly-coupled (updating both the model physics and BGC variables).

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In order to obtain optimized parameters, two types of experiments were conducted: First, parameter estimation was conducted in the 1D prototype using ERGOM configured for the station Arkona in the southern Baltic Sea. Second, parameter sensitivity runs were performed with the 3D NEMO-ERGOM-PDAF system.

For the parameter estimation in the 1D prototype, the same experimental setup was used as in WP4 (Deliverable 4.2) along with the same initial ensemble consisting of 40 states. Again, several model parameters for both physics (*surface u10 and v10* - wind speed in West-East and South-North direction scale factor, *turb_param k_min* - minimum turbulent kinetic energy) and biogeochemistry (*deltao* - Phytoplankton mortality rate, *graz* - Zooplankton grazing rate, *wpz* - Diatoms sinking velocity, *wbz* - Cyanobacteria sinking velocity, *nb* - Phytoplankton excretion rate, *nue* - Zooplankton respiration rate, *sigma_b* - Zooplankton mortality rate, *alphab* - Half-saturation constant of cyanobacteria, *alphaf* - Half-saturation constant of flagellates, *alphap* - Half-saturation constant of diatoms) were perturbed following the lognormal distribution with a variance of 0.2. The assimilative experiments performed daily assimilation of satellite surface chlorophyll observations using weakly coupled DA, (in contrast to WP4 real observations were assimilated here). We also performed experiments assimilating SST observations, either as only observation type or in combination with chlorophyll, however they produced incompatible results with chlorophyll-only assimilation and will not be shown here.

We performed five 1D-experiments (all for year 2016) as follows:

1. **FREE default:** In this experiment, the ensemble is run freely without assimilation using the default parameter values.
2. **CHL w default:** Weakly-coupled assimilation of the satellite surface chlorophyll observations for state estimation only using the default parameter values.
3. **CHL w default joint:** Weakly-coupled assimilation of the satellite surface chlorophyll observations using the default parameter values for a joint state and parameter estimation.
4. **FREE estimated:** In this experiment, the ensemble is run freely without assimilation using the parameter values estimated in experiment 3.
5. **CHL w estimated:** Weakly-coupled assimilation of the satellite surface chlorophyll observations for state estimation using the parameter values estimated in experiment 3.

Since only selected parameters are initially perturbed, the estimated parameters are limited to these. The selection takes into account the sensitivity analysis done in WP3.

Fig 3.1.1.1 shows the time series for six of the ten estimated BGC parameters. The slight offset between the initial parameter value for the DA-run and the default value is due to the parameter perturbation at the initial time step. Investigating the development of the parameters shows that most undergo seasonal effects. The strongest development in most parameters occurs during the peak bloom of cyanobacteria starting in July. Towards the end of the year, however, the parameters remain rather constant. Table 3.1.1.1 contains a summary of the estimated and default parameter values.

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Fig. 3.1.1.1 Timeseries of selected estimated model parameters (ensemble mean) from the jointly estimated state and parameter run (CHL w default joint), assimilating surface chlorophyll observations weakly-coupled (blue) along with the default parameter value (black).

To validate the effect of the estimated parameters, the surface chlorophyll is analyzed. Fig. 3.1.1.2 shows surface chlorophyll over the assimilation period (the year 2016) for all five experiments along with the assimilated satellite observations (left) and the log RMSe difference over time to the free run simulated with the default parameter values (right), where a negative difference implies an improvement towards the free run with default parameter values. The predominant difference obtained by the assimilation and the use of the estimated parameters occurs during the large bloom in July and the small bloom in October. However, observations are rather scarce after September. Thus, no conclusions regarding the quality can be drawn for that period. During the bloom in July, the free run with default parameters shows a clearly too high chlorophyll concentration. The concentration is reduced by the chlorophyll assimilation as well as for the free run with the estimated parameters. This improvement is further highlighted by the negative log RMSE difference. The lowest RMSE is obtained for the CHLw DA-run using the estimated parameters. The reduced concentration is expected since the assimilated chlorophyll observations are lower and additionally the estimated grazing rate is higher than the default, leading to reduced phytoplankton.

Fig. 3.1.1.2. Left: Surface chlorophyll for the five experiments and the assimilated satellite chlorophyll observations. Right: log RMSE for surface chlorophyll difference to the free run with default parameter values, where a negative log RMSE difference indicates a higher log RMSE for the free run with default parameter values compared to the DA-runs or free run with estimated parameter values.

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For the 3D NEMO-ERGOM system in the Baltic Sea we used the estimated parameter values from the 1D parameter estimation study (see Table 3.1.1.1). Since the ERGOM model in the 1D prototype is not identical to that in the 3D NEMO-ERGOM model, some modifications were required. In particular, the 3D ERGOM model has two different parameters for zooplankton grazing, while 1D ERGOM only has one such parameter. We used the parameter estimate from the 1D experiment to replace the parameter value of micro-zooplankton grazing, whose original value was closer to the estimate and kept the parameter of meso-zooplankton grazing unchanged. In addition, the parameter 'nue' only exists in the 1D model and was hence not used in the 3D model runs.

Figure 3.1.1.3 shows the effect of using the estimated parameters in the 3D model configuration. For the surface chlorophyll concentration at the station Arkona (Fig. 3.1.1.3 left), the use of the estimated parameter values led to an earlier spring bloom with a maximum in February compared to March with the default parameters. The maximum amplitude of the bloom is slightly lower than with the default parameters. Compared to the satellite observations, the bloom intensity is still too high, and it happens too early. The lower concentrations after the bloom are more consistent with the observations than in the case of the default parameters. The right-hand side of Fig. 3.1.1.3 shows the RMSE with regard to the satellite chlorophyll concentrations for the full Baltic Sea. When the estimated parameters are used, the RMSE is lower only during the first half of April than when using the default parameters. At other times, the RMSE from using the estimated parameters varies around the RMSE obtained with the default values. On average over the full experiment, the estimated parameters result in a reduction of the RMSE by 0.3%.

Parameter	Default value 1D	Default value 3D	Estimated parameter
alphap	0.4	0.5	0.413
alphaf	0.1	0.15	0.105
alphap	0.25	0.3	0.248
deltao	0.02	0.02	0.023
graz (3D:mizgraz)	0.5	0.4	0.539
nb	0.01	0.01	0.011
nue*	0.01	-	0.01
rb0	0.75	0.5	0.679
rf0	0.4	0.7	0.379
rp0	1.3	1.0	1.385
sigma_b	0.03	0.03	0.029

Table 3.1.1.1 Default parameter values in the 3D ERGOM configuration and used estimated parameter values from the 1D experiments. Parameters marked with an asterisk are not present in the 3D ERGOM model version.

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Fig. 3.1.1.3. Effect of using the estimated parameter values from the 1D experiment in the 3D NEMO-ERGOM model setup for the Baltic Sea. (left) surface chlorophyll concentration at the station Arkona at which the parameter estimation was computed. (right) root mean square error (RMSe) for the full Baltic Sea with regard to the satellite chlorophyll observations.

Given that the estimated parameter values resulted in an overly early bloom at the station Arkona and only a negligible reduction of the RMSE in the Baltic Sea, we performed additional 3D simulations in which we systematically modified the value of single parameters. For this we either multiplied the parameter by a factor of 1.1 or divided the parameter by this factor. The value of 1.1 followed the typical change in the parameter values that was obtained in the parameter estimation study before. The parameters were those listed in Table 3.1.1.1 and in addition the grazing parameter for meso-zooplankton (mezgraz) and three parameters regulating the sinking velocities. In addition, some runs have been performed in which combinations of parameters (e.g. all three maximum uptake parameters rp_0 , rb_0 , rf_0) have been varied. Overall, 41 parameter variation runs have been performed for the 4-month period January to April 2015. When varying the parameters not all had a visual influence at the station Arkona or the full Baltic. E.g. varying the initial slope parameters (alpha_b, alpha_f, alpha_p) or the sinking velocities (wbz, wdz, wpz) had only a negligible effect.

Figure 3.1.1.4 shows the effect of variations of single parameters that showed larger effects at the station Arkona. For example, varying the grazing parameter for micro-zooplankton changed the chlorophyll concentration from the end of February. Reducing the zooplankton grazing increases concentration, while increasing the grazing reduces the chlorophyll concentration. This is the expected result since increased grazing reduces the phytoplankton. In contrast to the grazing of micro-zooplankton, varying the grazing constant for meso-zooplankton had no influence. Apart from the zooplankton-related parameter, varying the maximum uptake rates for diatoms (rp_0) and flagellates (rf_0) changed the chlorophyll concentrations. Here, the parameter for the diatoms showed a larger influence before the bloom peak, while the parameter for the flagellates exhibits a larger influence after the peak of the bloom. Decreasing the parameter for diatoms, but increasing it for flagellates leads to a slightly lower overall chlorophyll concentration and hence lower deviation from the observations. However, all the parameter variations in the range of 10% only had a very small influence. The RMSE over the full Baltic Sea was only reduced by up to 1.7% (in the case that the parameter rf_0 was increased by 10%, see right hand side of Fig. 3.1.1.4). To this end, the parameter variation experiments are not sufficient to produce a new set of parameters. For this, parameter estimation utilizing the data assimilation system in 3D would be required, which was not in the scope of this WP.

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Fig. 3.1.1.4. Effect of selected parameter variations on concentration of surface chlorophyll at the station Arkona.

3.1.2 The experiments

The final reanalysis run was performed for the year 2015. Given that the parameter estimation in the 1D prototype and the parameter sensitivity experiments with the 3D system for the Baltic Sea did not result in clear improvements of the model results, the original model parameters, as used in the operational BAL-MFC system, were used. The experiments were initialized as described in deliverables 4.1 and 4.2. The assimilation was performed from February 1, 2015 until the end of the year. Both satellite data of sea surface temperature and chlorophyll observations were assimilated. The chlorophyll observations were assimilated weakly-coupled while the sea surface temperature observations were assimilated strongly-coupled.

3.2 The system in the GLO and IBI MFC domains

3.2.1 The R&D system set-up

This section describes the protocol of the best-performing assimilation experiments implemented by IGE/UGA in WP6 using the coupled NEMO-PISCES probabilistic model implemented in the GLO and IBI systems (see D3.1) and the 4D inverse method developed in SEAMLESS (see D3.4). We essentially follow the same experimental setup as the one used in WP3, assimilating only L3 ocean colour data given the weak impact of altimetry obtained in WP4. In this way, we can consistently examine the benefit of improved parameterizations with respect to WP3 experiments. The best-performing experimental protocol is as follows:

- Improved initialization of the prior coupled physical-biogeochemical model ensemble.** We generate a new 40-member ensemble during year 2019, assuming (as in WP3 and WP4) uncertainty sources originating from (i) critical biogeochemical model parameters of the PISCES stochastic model, (ii) sub-grid scale effects associated to $\frac{1}{4}^\circ$, eddy-permitting horizontal resolution, and (iii) location uncertainties of mesoscale structures and associated advective/diffusive fluxes, accounting for coupled physical/biogeochemical effects. However, we use as initial conditions the ensemble spread obtained at the end of the “first guess” ensemble experiment of WP3 (i.e. December 2019). In this way, a more realistic spread is used

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at the initial time to avoid another spin-up of the ensemble spread during the early bloom period.

- **Extended set of uncertain BGC model parameters.** The improved parameterization of the stochastic NEMO-PISCES model is obtained by accounting for a larger number of error sources related to uncertain BGC model parameters. Based on the outcome of the PISCES sensitivity studies performed in WP3 (see Deliverable 3.2) and additional tests, we identified 17 stochastic parameters (instead of 7 as used in WP3/WP4) to generate the new ensemble. The 10 additional parameters (see table below, right columns) are all related to the zooplankton and particulate organic matter dynamics, complementing the initial 7 uncertain parameters (see table below, left columns) that are mainly related to phytoplankton dynamics.

Uncertain PISCES parameters	ref value	Uncertain PISCES parameters	ref value
1. Temperature sensitivity of phyto growth	0.045	8. Maximum zoo grazing rate	3.0
2. Temperature sensitivity of zoo grazing	0.084	9. Maximum mesozoo grazing rate	0.75
3. Maximum phyto growth rate at 0°C	0.5	10. POC sinking speed	2.0
4. Photosynthetic efficiency of nano	4.0	11. Big particles sinking speed	50.0
5. Photosynthetic efficiency of diatoms	4.0	12. Exsudation rate of zooplankton	0.03
6. Dependence of nanophytoplankton on the day length	1.5	13. Microzoo preference for nanophyto	1.0
7. Dependence of diatoms on the day length	1.5	14. Remineralization rate of DOC	0.3
		15. Half-saturation constant of DOC remineralization	417.E-6
		16. Microzoo preference for POM	1.0
		17. Microzoo preference for diatoms	0.6

Tab.3.2.1.1: Parameters perturbed and estimated for the GLO/IBI domain.

- **State vector augmentation.** In addition to the model state variables included in the 4D space-time estimation vector, we have adopted a state vector augmentation technique, incorporating the 17 uncertain BGC parameters in the estimation vector to jointly compute the posterior space-time distribution of the BGC model state variables, ecosystem indicators and BGC model parameters.

Before running the full one-year experiment with the best-performing setup, we first conducted several 4-month sensitivity experiments in the PAP region to investigate the impact of ensemble size and forecast lead time on posterior estimations, as planned for Task 6.2. Ocean colour L3 data available between March 15th and May 15th are assimilated in the full prior 39-member (one of the 40-ensemble members was found corrupted and therefore unusable) and in a truncated 26-member ensembles to compute posterior estimates. The period between May 15th and June 15th is used to assess the statistical forecast performance, as already done in WP3.

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Figure 3.2.1.1: Hindcast/forecast time series of estimated trophic efficiency (ratio of vertically integrated values of total zooplankton and phytoplankton biomass between 0- and 200- meter depth) at PAP station, for the posterior 26-member ensemble (left panel) and posterior 39-member ensemble (right panel) ensembles. The black curves show the ensemble members; the green curve is the ensemble mean; the red curve is the standard deviation (std). L3 OC data are assimilated only between March 15th and May 15th; the probabilistic forecast starts on May 16th.

Time series of 3 ecosystem indicators (POC flux at 100 m depth, trophic efficiency and vertically-integrated primary production) at PAP station were considered as a benchmark to assess the impact of ensemble size. Figure 3.2.1.1 here above illustrates that only small differences are obtained between 26-member or 39-member ensemble estimates of trophic efficiency for what concerns the period and area of interest. However, experiments performed with smaller ensemble size show degraded performances. The same behaviour is observed for the other 2 indicators. Hence, we conclude that an ensemble size of 39 members corresponds to converged statistics and is the most suitable for the best-performing, full-year experiments exploited in Section 4. This sensitivity study also shows that, if computing costs become an issue in MFC systems, an analysis of the performance of smaller-size ensembles (~ 26 members) is worth being conducted in the perspective of operational production.

3.2.2 The experiments

The best performing experiment is implemented for the year 2019 using the 4D inversion scheme developed in WP3 (Popov et al, 2023) to generate posterior distribution estimates of the joint model state, ecosystem indicators and model parameters in 3 regions that correspond to contrasted biogeochemical regimes of the North Atlantic ocean basin. The ensemble spread is initialized on January 1st 2019, using the prior ensemble already generated in WP3 to account for initial uncertainties. Daily CMEMS L3 ocean colour products are assimilated over the full annual period to generate posterior estimates of the BGC state variables and the 17 uncertain BGC parameters, in addition to the POC, Trophic Efficiency and Primary Production indicators.

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3.3 The system in the MED MFC domain

3.3.1 The R&D system set-up

Following the validation performed in D3.4, D4.1 and D5.1 reports, as part of SEAMLESS WP3-WP5, OGS has chosen the following (best performing) configuration to represent SEAMLESS target indicators on the CMEMS MED domain: (i) OGS used the ensemble developments from WP3 for the biogeochemical assimilation, and (ii) OGS implemented the multi-platform DA capacity developed and tested in WP5.

Within WP6, OGS performed 1D parameter assimilation experiments along BGC-Argo float tracks following a similar procedure as Terzic et al. (2019), with the purpose to demonstrate the feasibility of estimation of BFM parameters using BGC-Argo floats and to test the 3D BFM model with optimized parameters. For each of the available floats fully operational during 2019, using the EAT tool, we performed a parameter assimilation procedure, separately correcting, with a dedicated assimilation experiment, each of the parameters identified in the WP3. The top ten sensitive parameters were related to light, microzooplankton and diatoms. We used 9 available BGC-Argo floats for the assimilation experiment, two of them in the West Mediterranean, 6 in the east Mediterranean and one in the south Adriatic. The experiments were based on the assimilation of chlorophyll measured along the vertical BGC-Argo profiles. The results of the assimilation were particularly relevant for light group parameters. They were impacted by the assimilation showing convergence toward realistic values, while other parameters diverged toward boundary values. In particular, we considered the light attenuation background coefficient that is the most relevant parameter resulted in the sensitivity analysis of deliverable D3.2 and that showed realistic impacts on deep chlorophyll maximum (DCM) in the 1D parameter assimilation experiments. The attenuation background coefficient is used in the monochromatic 1D SEAMLESS prototype implementation of the OGSTM-BFM to account for the light attenuation by water and all the non-phytoplankton coloured matter.

The result based on different BGC Argo floats provides a map with a distribution of the parameter varying both in time and space along each BGC Argo Float, shown in Fig 3.3.1.1. The values of the corrected parameters were used to construct space-time-dependent maps assigning weekly-varying corrected parameters to the corresponding Copernicus Marine Service sub-basins for the Mediterranean Sea. For each sub-basin and for each week, the corrected parameter was calculated as the spatial average of the 1D assimilation experiment results. In sub-basins without available BGC-Argo floats, the parameter was set constant and equal to the parameter before the EAT assimilation experiments.

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Figure 3.3.1.1 Distribution of the light attenuation background coefficient expressed in m^{-1} corrected by means of the assimilation procedure using the 1D tool and the BGC-Argo float data for the year 2019.

To evaluate the effects of the optimized light attenuation parameter derived from BGC-Argo observations compared with the one based on satellite observations used in the Copernicus Marine Service reanalysis, we considered: (i) a 3D hindcast simulation (T0) with a constant light attenuation background parameter and simulated phytoplankton attenuation, used before the assimilation performed in the 1D experiments, (ii) a 3D hindcast simulation using the spatio-temporally varying optimized light attenuation background parameter (TOPT) and simulated phytoplankton attenuation, both compared with (iii) the reanalysis simulation considered as the best available reconstruction of the biogeochemical state (REA). The reanalysis assimilates satellite chlorophyll and attenuates light based on satellite product accounting for every shading effect in the water column, i.e., water, coloured matter and phytoplankton. Results of this preliminary analysis showed (Fig.3.3.1.2) that the hindcast simulation using the optimized parameters provides improved results matching better the reanalyses chlorophyll temporal evolution at different depths.

Figure 3.3.1.2 Effects on surface chlorophyll concentration of using the corrected parameter on a test hindcast simulation using time and space dependent maps of the background extrapolated from 1D assimilation. Results of 2019 in the whole Mediterranean Sea (left column) and in three sub-basins (nwm, tyr and lev2; panels below the map). REA (red solid lines) are

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the reanalysis products, T0 (green solid lines) are the simulation using non corrected parameter and the TOPT (magenta solid lines) are the simulations using the optimized parameter. Correlation coefficient and RMSD comparing T0 and TOPT with REA are reported for each timeseries in each panel.

The assimilation and correction of the light attenuation parameter produce interesting results in terms of chlorophyll correction. Impacts are detectable in areas where BGC-Argo observations are available (e.g., tyr2 and lev2 in Fig. 3.3.2) and are larger in the subsurface layer (50 m) in winter and in a deeper layer (100 m) in summer. The seasonal variability of the layers with larger impacts is consistent with two seasonal features of the Mediterranean phytoplankton dynamics: in winter the subsurface layer is dominated by the winter mixed bloom, while in summer deeper layers display DCMs. On the other hand, in areas where the optimized parameter was not inserted (due to the lack of BGC-Argo floats) no improvements on chlorophyll are obtained. In summary, the 3D simulation using the optimized parameter performs as well as the Marine Copernicus reanalysis that used light attenuation parameter based on satellite observations. However, these improvements are limited to the areas where enough BGC-Argo floats are available, while some degradations with respect to the Copernicus reanalysis are detected in areas without the optimized light attenuation parameter. Therefore, we decided to run the WP6 final simulation keeping the formulation for this critical parameter as in WP3.

In particular, the final simulation is based on the 24-member ensemble system from WP3 with perturbations of parameters and initial conditions. Moreover, multiplatform assimilation in an ensemble framework (WP5 activities) is implemented in the final simulation with daily assimilation of satellite and BGC-Argo chlorophyll.

3.3.2 The experiments

The final reanalysis was run for the year 2019, assimilating CMEMS satellite surface total chlorophyll, as well as BGC-Argo data for chlorophyll. The BGC-Argo float observations were from the Mediterranean Sea operational database for the 2019. All the ensemble members were initialized on the 01/01/2019 by a PCA approach. Each ensemble member has its own initial condition, computed from a 20-years hindcast simulation:

- 20 days before and after the 1st of January are taken into account for each year;
- the variability expressed by the selected dates is chosen as a proxy of the uncertainty of the state vector at 1/1/2019, first day of the WP6 simulation;
- a multivariate principal component analysis (PCA) has been computed using 64 HPC nodes on the CINECA's GALILEO100 supercomputer;
- the PCA takes into account the log-concentrations of all the states variables, weighted to focus on surface chlorophyll variability;
- the most relevant 23 components are a base of the error subspace;
- 24 ensemble members are sampled from the base, using a high order sampling method, namely the GHOSH sampling (Spada et al. 2023).

Although the reanalysis is 1 year, we present only the results from March 2019 and August 2019 to capture two representative periods of the seasonal variability. The considered indicators are the one described in Deliverable 3.2.

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3.4 The system in the ARC MFC domain

3.4.1 The R&D system set-up

Following the 3D data assimilation studies with the CMEMS ARC MFC biogeochemical data assimilation system conducted and reported in SEAMLESS WP3 (D3.4) and WP5 (D5.1), the following experiment settings and metrics are chosen to meet the SEAMLESS WP6 objectives and SEAMLESS target indicators: (i) Inter comparison between ensemble Kalman smoother data assimilation experiments with and without parameter estimation. (ii) Perturbing and estimating eight BGC model parameters: growth rate of large phytoplankton (grPl), growth rate of small phytoplankton (grPs), mortality rate of large phytoplankton (mrPl), mortality rate of small phytoplankton (mrPs), mortality rate of large zooplankton (mrZl), mortality rate of small zooplankton (mrZs), sinking rate of detritus and opal (srDO) and Carbon to Silicate ratio, for estimation (CrSi). (iii) Use of the phytoplankton phenology and phytoplankton functional types (PFT) among the SEAMLESS target indicators for evaluating the intercomparison experiments in i).

The 3D data assimilation system is as previously described in D5.1 assimilating satellite chlorophyll concentration and in situ nutrients (Figure 3.4.1.1). The BGC Argo profiles used in D5.1 are excluded from the experiments here.

1D EAT experiments for parameter estimation showed large discrepancy in model bias in physical models between GOTM and HYCOM in the Arctic Region and subsequent bias in the ocean surface chlorophyll phenology. In our preliminary parameter optimization experiments based on parsac, it required nudging temperature and salinity profiles to Argo float data to reduce the model bias in the mixed layer development. However, our 3D system does not include such system yet and this indicates the parameters tuned for 1D system are not necessarily optimal for the 3D system. Because of these reasons the 1D experiments were not used to calibrate the 3D system, rather than that we used directly the 3D joint parameter-state assimilation to improve the parameters. Since model bias is specific to our current 3D system setting, the parameters estimated in 3D presented here should be interpreted carefully. For example, consistent patterns in seasonal cycle of estimated parameters over the five years experiments in Figure 3.4.2.1 only indicate pattern of model bias against observation is consistent over the five years.

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Figure 3.4.1.1. ARC MFC model domain and sample satellite Chlorophyll concentration from ESA OC CCI 8 days composite data on May 1st 2007 (left panel). Composite locations (green dots) of in situ nutrients (nitrate, silicate and phosphate) available in the Arctic Ocean between 2000 and 2015 (right panel).

The assimilation experiments with parameter estimation cover the years from 2007 to 2011 for studying the seasonal timeseries of the estimated parameters. Control data assimilation experiments without parameter estimations were also conducted for the years 2007, 2008 and 2009. The assimilation window length is set to 8 days and the period of assimilation is set to the spring and fall phytoplankton bloom period in the ARC MFC domain, from March to October, in every experiment. The set of BGC model parameters and their default settings are listed in Table 3.4.1.1. The amplitude of the Gaussian error for each parameter is set to 20% relative to the respective default value. The Minimum and maximum values are both set to avoid unrealistic model behaviour.

Since the current ARC MFC products is based on a joint state-parameter estimation system, the evaluation of the parameter estimation system is conducted against a control data assimilation experiment performed without parameter estimation. The impact of parameter estimation on phytoplankton phenology was evaluated by comparing the surface chlorophyll concentration from the analysis to satellite ocean color data. the impact of parameter estimation on phytoplankton functional type was evaluated by comparing the ARC MFC system against the control experiment and observational information from the literature. Note that the phytoplankton functional type is not currently part of the ARC MFC products and is evaluated for the first time in this study. 80 ensemble members are generated for data assimilation with the ensemble Kalman smoother and for the ensemble model forecast as described in D5.1.

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Parameter [unit]	grPl [1/day]	grPs [1/day]	mrPl [1/day]	mrPs [1/day]	mrZ l [1/day]	mrZ s [1/day]	srDO [m/day]	CrSi [molC/molSi]
Error [%]	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
Min	0.8	0.5	0.02	0.02	0.05	0.05	3.5	3.0
Max	3.0	2.0	0.25	0.25	0.4	0.4	20.0	13.0
Default value	1.27	1.099	0.039	0.079	0.097	0.199	5.049	6.752

Table 3.4.1.1 List of BGC model parameters. *grPl*: growth rate of large phytoplankton. *grPs*: growth rate of small phytoplankton. *mrPl*: mortality rate of large phytoplankton. *mrPs*: mortality rate of small phytoplankton. *mrZl*: mortality rate of large zooplankton. *mrZs*: mortality rate of small zooplankton. *srDO*: sinking rate of detritus and opal. *CrSi*: Carbon to Silicate ratio.

3.4.2 The experiments

Model ensemble members are generated for each year by starting the ensemble model spin up run one year ahead of the targeted experiment year. For example, for data assimilation experiment conducted in 2007, the ensemble generation without data assimilation starts from 2006 January 1st with perturbations of atmospheric fields (wind forcing, downward shortwave radiation for PAR in BGC model) and perturbations of BGC model parameters. All perturbations follow a Gaussian white noise and temporal evolution of the parameters between analysis times is described by AR(1) process. In the control experiments without parameter estimation, the perturbation in the model parameters is turned off. Any model parameters falling beyond the lower or upper limit after ensemble generation or after parameter estimation is pushed back to its limit value.

3.5 The system in the NWES MFC domain

3.5.1 The R&D system set-up

Following the validation performed in D3.4, D4.1-4.2 and D5.1 reports, as part of SEAMLESS WP3-WP5, PML has chosen the following (best performing) configuration to represent SEAMLESS target indicators on the CMEMS NWS domain: (i) PML used the ensemble developments from WP3, as well as the ensemble-variational DA system based on those developments, (ii) due to underperformance of the coupled physical-biogeochemical DA, PML applied the WP3 developments only to the biogeochemical assimilation, (iii) PML implemented the multi-platform DA capacity developed and tested in WP5.

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To be more concrete, the 30-member ensemble system from WP3 is based on ERSEM parameter perturbations, ERA5 atmospheric forcing ensemble and observation perturbations. After the WP3 developments, PML did some re-adjustments to the perturbations of ERSEM parameters by including additional parameters to the scheme. The new parameters were chosen based on a specific target indicator being most sensitive to their value, despite their significance being relatively low when averaged across all the indicators. The reason for this update was that we wanted to make sure that no indicator was discriminated by the choice of model parameters. Based on this, PML has expanded the list of perturbed ERSEM parameters from six to the nine listed in Table 3.5.1.1. The bacteria and diatom parameters from Table 3.5.1.1 were perturbed already in WP3-WP5, the dinoflagellate, nanophytoplankton and DOM parameter perturbations were added in this work. As in WP3-WP5, the parameter values were drawn from a uniform distribution within an interval of +/- 30% around the "optimal" parameter value presented in Tab. 3.5.1.1. In addition to those, PML also included new perturbations to the physical NEMO model, i.e. spatio-temporally varying perturbations to the stochastic kinetic energy scheme and to the vertical mixing parameters (similar to the ones in Lea et al 2022).

Variable	Parameter	FABM notation	Pre-SEAMLESS value	SEAMLESS value
Bacteria	The efficiency at high oxygen levels	B1:pu	0.6	0.672
	The maximum turn-over rate of DOM	B1:sR1	1 1/d	0.746 1/d
	Fraction of semi-refractory POC available to bacteria	B1:rR2	0.0075	0.008
Diatoms	Threshold for nitrogen limitation	P1:xqcn	1	0.829
	Maximum specific productivity at reference temperature	P1:sum	1.375 1/d	1.685 1/d
	Maximum nitrogen-to-carbon ratio	P1:xqn	1.075	0.981
Dino-flagellates	Threshold for nitrogen limitation	P4:xqcn	1	1.169
Nanophyto-plankton	Threshold for nitrogen limitation	P2:xqcn	1	1.223
small size POM	Sinking velocity	R4:rm	1 m/d	0.895 m/d

Tab. 3.5.1.1: The list of ERSEM parameters optimized in the WP6.2 and perturbed. We list both their pre-SEAMLESS, and the improved, SEAMLESS, value recommended for CMEMS MFC use on the NWS domain.

In WP6 PML has run joint parameter-state assimilation experiments at the 1D L4 location, with the purpose to better estimate ERSEM parameter values. The DA estimation has however led to highly temporally variable parameter values and thus taking the mean value of the parameter time-series was not representative of the time-series themselves. Using mean values of the assimilated parameters has then led to substantial decline in the model skill. Alternative approach was subsequently chosen, by directly running the free run ensemble in 3D and assessing the skill of the

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different ensemble members against observations. The optimal parameter choice was based on comparing the model surface chlorophyll with the abundant satellite ocean-color-derived chlorophyll observations. It is known that the ERSEM model has significant issues with phenology, i.e. showing late spring blooms with large magnitude of chlorophyll, as well as too low winter surface chlorophyll concentrations (for all see Skakala et al 2018,2020,2022). As phytoplankton phenology is a strong driver of biogeochemistry on the NWS, and can be robustly validated, we focused on the model skill in representing surface chlorophyll during the bloom period. The Fig.3.5.1.1 shows skill comparisons of the 30 different model parametrizations with respect to phenology. The improved parameter values (together with the old ones) are shown in Table 3.5.1.1, with Fig.3.5.1.2 comparing the surface chlorophyll time-series between the pre-SEAMLESS, the new (SEAMLESS) parametrization, and the OC-CCI v5.0 (unbiased) satellite observations.

Fig.3.5.1.1 The magnitude of phytoplankton bloom measured in surface chlorophyll concentration (mean across NWS in mg/m^3) vs the timing of the bloom in days. The colorbar shows the concentration of chlorophyll (mean across NWS in mg/m^3) on the 01/03/2018, providing a closest proxy for chlorophyll winter values. The earlier bloom with lower magnitude, corresponding to higher winter concentrations is the direction in which the observations indicate the model improvement. The different plotted values are the 30 different ensemble members.

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Fig.3.5.1.2: Surface chlorophyll averaged across the NWS (full lines) comparing pre-SEAMLESS and SEAMLESS parametrization with satellite observations. The dotted lines show the surface chlorophyll mean only across the locations of the satellite data on the NWS. The simulation was for March-June 2018.

3.5.2 The experiments

The final reanalysis was run for the year 2018, assimilating OC-CCI v5.0 satellite surface total chlorophyll, as well as glider data for chlorophyll and oxygen. The glider observations were from the AlterEco mission that took place in the central North Sea throughout 2018. All the ensemble members were initialized on the 01/01/2018 by a deterministic assimilative run from Skakala et al 2022. Although the reanalysis is 1 year, we present only the results from March 2018 onwards, since the first two simulation months are considered to be merely a spin-up of the ensemble.

4. Results

4.1 The BAL MFC domain

4.1.1 Validation of the reanalysis

The final (one-year, 2015) run shows a second slightly smaller peak for surface chlorophyll concentration over the months August and September at both stations Arkona and Darss Sill (Fig. 4.1.1.1). Similar to the first peak in February-March, discussed in Deliverables 4.1 and 4.2, the surface chlorophyll concentration is much lower in the observations than in the model for the second bloom. Hence, the model overestimates the bloom. The strongly-coupled assimilation of SST in combination with weakly-coupled assimilation of CHL data reduces the concentration as expected. At the station Darss Sill, this reduction is also in line with the in situ observations at a depth of 2m. Besides the effect

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of a lower surface chlorophyll concentration, the timing of the second bloom is slightly shifted to an earlier time period for both stations. Here, the observed beginning of the bloom is at the beginning of July, while it only starts in August for the free run. For the CHLw+SSTs DA-run, this timing is corrected.

Towards the end of the year, satellite observations become rather scarce due to clouds. In December, no observations are available at all. Towards the end of October, where still some observations are present, a minor third bloom seems to occur at both stations. Here, the free and the DA-run show the same timing as well as chlorophyll concentrations. However, the chlorophyll concentrations remain rather high after the peak for the CHLw+SSTs DA-run, while it drops more significantly for the free run. Since no satellite observations are available during that time, we can only validate with the in situ data at Darss Sill, where the observations are in line with the slightly higher concentrations estimated by the DA-run. Overall, the RMSE at the Darss Sill is reduced from 1.628 mg Chl/m³ in the free run to 1.061 mg Chl/m³ in the DA-run when comparing with the assimilated satellite data and from 1.227 mg Chl/m³ in the free run to 1.059 mg Chl/m³ in the DA-run when using the in situ data at depth 2m. At the station Arkona, where only satellite observations are available, the RMSE is reduced from 1.560 mg Chl/m³ in the free run to 0.669 mg Chl/m³ in the CHLw+SSTs DA-run.

Fig. 4.1.1.1 Time series for chlorophyll at the station Darss Sill at the surface (a) and at a depth of 2m (b) as well as at station Arkona at the surface (c). The blue line represents the free run, while the black line corresponds to the CHLw+SSTs DA-run. The pluses and dots represent satellite and in situ observations, respectively.

Investigating the effect of the assimilation over the entire grid for example in September 2015 in Fig. 4.1.1.2 shows strong spatial differences. The free run shows very low concentrations in the Northern Baltic Sea while remaining higher concentrations in the South in the monthly average. This is in contrast to the satellite observations, which show higher concentrations in the North and lower concentrations in the South. The assimilation improved the chlorophyll field by increasing surface chlorophyll concentrations in the North and reducing them in the Southern part of the Baltic. The changes are up to 8 mg Chl/m³.

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Fig. 4.1.1.2. Monthly mean surface chlorophyll in September for a) Satellite observations, b) Free run and c) difference between CHLw + SSTs DA-run and Free run

Over the entire assimilation period, February until December 2015, the log RMSE for surface chlorophyll calculated over the entire Baltic Sea using the assimilated satellite observations shows strong improvements over the time (see Fig. 4.1.1.3). Especially during the months of the second bloom, August and September, the log RMSE is reduced significantly. During November however, the log RMSE of the CHLw+SSTs run gets closer to the free run log RMSE due to the scarcity of the observations during that period.

Fig. 4.1.1.3. Time series of logarithmic RMSE for surface chlorophyll over the entire grid calculated with the assimilated satellite chlorophyll observations. Towards the end of the year, no observations were available. The blue line corresponds to the free run, while the grey line refers to the CHLw+SSTs run in the analysis step and black to the forecast.

4.1.2 The MFC products for the target indicators

The SEAMLESS indicators at station Arkona over the year 2015 are displayed in Fig. 4.1.2.1. For pH and dissolved surface oxygen, the assimilation effect is rather insignificant. For primary production, assimilating the chlorophyll surface observations weakly-coupled and the sea surface temperature data strongly-coupled leads to lower values during the second bloom in August and September compared to the free run. This is in line with the lower chlorophyll concentrations during that period. The PFT ratio shows lower values for the case CHLw+SSTs than for the free run during the first half of the year, and higher values after July up to a difference of around 0.5 in November. As described in WP4, the concentration of diatoms is lower in the first half of the year for the free run, while cyanobacteria are not present at all for both runs and flagellates appear only slightly less for the free run, leading to an overall lower PFT ratio. For the second half of the year, and especially in

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November, the diatom concentration is higher than for the free run, which shows almost no diatoms during the winter months. In addition, the assimilation leads to a reduced concentration of cyanobacteria and flagellates during that time, explaining the strongly increased PFT ratio. For trophic efficiency, we also see different behaviour between the spring, summer and winter months. While the TE is increased by the assimilation in the months February until April, it is decreased between May and July and October until December. From May until July, mesozooplankton is reduced to almost zero for CHLw+SSTs, while micro zooplankton is reduced from May to July. Diatoms are especially reduced in comparison to the free run in May and June, cyanobacteria are increased in July and flagellates are decreased from May until July. All in all, this leads to a lower TE. The same behaviour is observed in the winter months, explaining the lower TE in October, November and December.

Fig. 4.1.2.1. SEAMLESS indicators over time at station Arkona.

4.2 The IBI and GLO MFC domains

The best-performing 4D regional inversions are computed over the full year (2019) into 3 key areas of the North Atlantic basin defined as follows (see figure 4.2.1.1): (i) the PAP region (144°N – 64°N x 31°W – 11°W), located in the overlap region of the GLO and IBI domains, is identical to previous experiments from WP3/WP4; (ii) the BATS region (27°N – 37°N x 69°W – 59°W) extends the 1-D sensitivity studies performed in WP3.2 at BATS station; (iii) the MUP (Mauritania UPwelling, 10°N – 25°N x 25°W – 15°W) region covers the highly productive West-African upwelling system.

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In this way we can analyse the estimated SEAMLESS indicators in three contrasted ecosystem provinces of the North Atlantic basin.

Figure 4.2.1.1: *Regions considered for the best-performing inversions*

4.2.1 Validation of the posterior estimates

The 4D inverse method used to produce the final reanalysis relies on state vector augmentation to simultaneously estimate ecosystem indicators and the 17 uncertain PISCES model parameters listed in Tab.3.2.1.1, with updated uncertainties.

Figure 4.2.1.2 illustrates the temporal evolution of prior/posterior phytoplankton growth rate parameter at PAP station, based on the stochastic parameterizations described in D3.3 and the average value of 0.5 day^{-1} corresponding to the PISCES reference value. The posterior estimates exhibit a strong reduction of uncertainty from April to August, while it remains almost unchanged during the two first and last months of the reanalysis (a similar behaviour is observed with all 17 stochastic parameters) and is weakly reduced during the autumn bloom. The growth rate ensemble remains centred around the reference value most of the time, while the mean value tends to increase during the two productive periods. Based on this single ensemble experiment, it is unclear if the temporal variability of the posterior distribution can be interpreted as a meaningful seasonal change of phytoplankton physiology, a limited representation of species diversity in the model or some compensation effect due to other unconsidered error sources. Nevertheless, using a constant value for this parameter would be an equally difficult option to justify given the complexity of the North Atlantic ecosystem.

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Figure 4.2.1.2: Prior (left) and posterior (right) ensemble distribution of PISCES phytoplankton growth rate parameter and standard deviation at PAP station (Reference value = 0.5 day⁻¹).

The verification of the posterior surface chlorophyll time series in the 3 target regions is based on CMEMS L4 ocean colour data products that are not used to perform the 4D inversions (the number of BGC-ARGO floats available in the considered domains were too few to make consistent verifications). These L4 data are not fully independent from the L3 data used for inversions, though the methods used to generate them are sufficiently different to derive meaningful conclusions.

Figure 4.2.2.1: Prior (upper row) and posterior (lower row) ensemble time series of surface chlorophyll (in mg/m³) in the PAP (left), BATS (centre) and MUP (right) regions. The black curves show the 39-member ensemble; the green curve is the ensemble mean; the blue curve is the L4 CMEMS OC product collocated at PAP; the red curve is the standard deviation.

In the PAP region, the posterior shows a much improved spring bloom development in terms of ensemble mean and reduced spread. Comparisons with the corresponding time series obtained in WP3 (see figure 4.2.2 of D3.4) indicate that the best-performing setup produces reduced posterior ensemble uncertainties. For instance, the ratio between posterior and prior ensemble variance on May 15th averaged over the PAP area is 0.077 here, instead of 0.118 in the demonstration experiments of WP3. This suggests that adding error sources by increasing the number of uncertain BGC parameters is likely to generate reduced uncertainties at least on the observed variables. In the BATS

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region, the prior ensemble was exhibiting a systematic overestimation of the surface production, mostly during the first 6 months of the year. The assimilated L3 observations enable to reduce the bias almost entirely. Additionally, we have observed a subsurface chlorophyll that looks consistent with climatology. The MUP region is typical of an upwelling system that exhibits intermittent variability essentially driven by wind events and their ocean response in terms of vertical velocity and surface circulation off the coast. The posterior reanalysis shows that only a few productive events can be constrained by L3 OC observations, with lower reduced uncertainties compared to the other two regions. We interpret this result as the manifestation of uncertainties in the surface wind forcing, not taken into account here. The MUP region is therefore probably an ideal site for studying the performance of an inversion system that would account for errors in the forcings.

4.2.2 The production of posterior target indicators

Figure 4.2.2.1 here above suggests that the retrieval of phenology indicators based on time series of surface chlorophyll concentration can be robustly estimated for PAP region, while it is definitely not suited to characterize BATS and MUP regions. We additionally computed the posterior distributions of net Primary Production, POC vertical flux at 100 m and Trophic Efficiency in the 3 regions as shown in Figure 4.2.2.2. For the PAP region, the annual cycle has similarities to the one obtained with a reduced set of uncertainty source but also significant differences, mostly during the post summer bloom (see figure 4.2.7 in D3.4). For the BATS region, the under-dispersed posterior ensemble suggests that key error sources are neglected in the considered region in spite of the good fit with L4 data sets. For the MUP region, it will be required to first controlling the ocean response to surface wind before assessing the value of the computed indicators given the moderate success of the reconstructed chlorophyll.

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Figure 4.2.2.2: Ensemble time series of (i) vertically integrated total Primary Production (in mg.C/m²/day, left column), (ii) downward Flux of the Particulate Organic Carbon at 100-meter depth (in mg.C/m²/day, centred column); (iii) Trophic Efficiency (ratio of vertically integrated values of total zooplankton and phytoplankton biomass between 0- and 200- meter depth, right column). The results are shown for the PAP region (upper row), BATS region (middle row) and MUP region (bottom row). The black curves show the 39-member posterior ensemble; the green curve is the ensemble mean; the red curve is the standard deviation.

In conclusion, several remaining challenges relevant to the GLO and IBI MFCs can be highlighted by the inversions carried out in the 3 regions.

1°) The regional 4D inversion system finally obtained by refining the modelling, uncertainty parameterisations and inversion choices seems to produce robust results in the PAP region which is illustrative of the IBI region. However, the generalisation of these choices to the North Atlantic Ocean basin / GLO is far from trivial given the variety of BGC regimes and error sources to be taken into account. The objective of an assimilation system that could be generalised to the global ocean is probably just as challenging and comparable to the scientific developments that were necessary to establish the PISCES modelling framework.

2°) Identifying the dominant sources of error is an ongoing challenge that needs to be addressed first and foremost, and which takes priority over other issues such as the minimum ensemble size to be used for quantifying uncertainties and performing inversions. We were able to show that it was possible to use ensembles of modest size (26 members) without significantly degrading the indicator estimates (uncertainty estimates seem to be more sensitive to the size of the ensembles) as long as the relevant error sources can be captured.

3°) The quantity of observations required to obtain robust inversions and to verify their robustness remains globally undersized in relation to the complexity of the systems implemented and

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the indicators to be produced according to user needs. This has often led us to be unable to verify the inversion results obtained. It is therefore important to continue thinking about the enhancement of observation systems, in a way that is closely related with the products and reliability needed.

4.3 The MED MFC domain

4.3.1 Validation of the reanalysis

The validation of reanalysis performed comparing free run ensemble simulation (HC) and DA ensemble simulation (DA) versus surface satellite chlorophyll data, Fig.4.3.1.1. In DA ensemble simulations, the comparison with satellite is calculated at the time right before the assimilation. For both HC and DA the root mean square difference (RMS) is lower in the summer period, when chlorophyll concentration is also lower. In both seasons the assimilation impacts are relatively low (low differences in RMS values). Nevertheless, the assimilation run shows always improvements: 5% of RMS reduction is achieved in all sub-basins except for TYR1, TYR2, ION1, LEV2, LEV3, LEV4. In summer, the effect of DA never deteriorates model skill, and there is a general improvement at Mediterranean scale with 5% RMS reduction. The results are successful in the fact that we finalized the first stable 1-year ensemble assimilation run on 3D Mediterranean scale without degradations. While further tuning is envisaged to increase the assimilation impacts, the large computational costs has limited the number of performed tests in WP6.

Fig.4.3.1.1: Root mean square (RMS) [mg chl/m³] with respect to satellite observations for winter (left) and summer (right) for 16 sub-basins and the whole Mediterranean Sea.

4.3.2 The MFC products for the target indicators

Ensemble mean and standard deviation of the target indicators have been calculated along 2019. Figure 4.3.2.1 and Fig. 4.3.2.2 show results of surface chlorophyll and primary production in two months: March, late-winter surface bloom conditions, and August, summer stratified conditions. The maps of target indicator mean are consistent with the known seasonal dynamics of the Mediterranean Sea: larger surface chlorophyll concentration in winter, summer primary production lower on average

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than in winter but with patches of considerable productivity. The analyses indicate that the absolute uncertainty is higher in more dynamical areas and time periods (e.g., chlorophyll standard deviation in the northwestern Mediterranean in winter), the range of variability of standard deviation is nearly 10% with respect to the range of variability of the average values.

PFT ratio, and POC, Fig.4.3.2.3 and Fig.4.3.2.4, show a coherent picture with respect to chlorophyll and primary production, with a west-east gradient showing larger phytoplankton in the western sub-basin. The maximum of PFT ratio and POC in the western Mediterranean are correlated. Similar uncertainty range is observed for chlorophyll and NPP with an increase of patchy structures for standard deviation during summer period. Trophic efficiency, Fig.4.3.2.5, shows a bimodal distribution with higher than one values in most of the areas with the exception during the winter period of the marginal seas (Adriatic and Aegean). Also, in this case the ensemble variability is lower than 10% with respect to the average.

Overall, even considering the 20% perturbation of the parameters applied in the simulations the ensemble indicators appear very stable, this is clear also observing the chlorophyll timeseries, Fig.4.3.2.6, where the spread is low with a small increase in sub-surface chlorophyll at 75 and 120 m depth.

Fig. 4.3.2.1: Ensemble mean of surface [0-5m] chlorophyll concentration (top) and ensemble standard deviation (bottom) in March 2019 (left) and August 2019 (right) computed over the 24 members simulation.

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Fig.4.3.2.2: Ensemble mean of 0-200 m integrated net primary production (top) and ensemble standard deviation (bottom) in March 2019 (left) and August 2019 (right) computed over the 24 members simulation.

Fig.4.3.2.3: Phytoplankton Functional Types (PFT ratio) indicator defined here as the ratio between large phytoplankton biomass and total phytoplankton biomass averaged in the 0-200 m layer. Ensemble average (top) and ensemble standard deviation (bottom) in March 2019 (left) and August 2019 (right) are computed over the 24 members simulation.

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Fig.4.3.2.4: Ensemble mean of 0-200 m average POC (top) and ensemble standard deviation (bottom) in March 2019 (left) and August 2019 (right) computed over the 24 members simulation.

Fig.4.3.2.5: Trophic efficiency (TE) defined as the ratio of production at one trophic level to production at the next lower trophic level, here approximated by the ratio between biomass of zooplankton and phytoplankton. Biomasses were vertically integrated in the 0-200m layer in deep ocean waters. The TE ensemble average (top) and ensemble standard deviation (bottom) in March 2019 (left) and August 2019 (right) are computed over the 24 members simulation.

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Fig.4.3.2.6: Chlorophyll time series at four depths (surface, 50 m, 75 m, 120 m) averaged over the Mediterranean Sea (MED), the North-Western Mediterranean (NWM) and the northern Levantine (LEV2).

4.4 The ARC MFC domain

4.4.1 Validation of the reanalysis

The validation of the reanalysis products by the ARC MFC system is conducted by their comparison against observation and against control experiments. Here we have a set of two control experiments: 1. ensemble free run, 2. data assimilation analysis without parameter estimation. The reanalysis product is evaluated at the end of the 8-days model forecast following the analysis and just before the next data assimilation analysis. The choice of this evaluation timing is made since the impact of state and parameter estimation to the reanalysis product has highest sensitivity just before a data assimilation analysis.

The ensemble means of the estimated parameters are plotted for different years in Figure 4.4.1.1. The seasonal cycles of the parameters, estimated independently for the 5 years, show common tendencies in general, but the years may differ from parameter to parameter. The most robust estimation across all years can be found for grPI for the entire analysis period and grPs until June. The estimates of both growth rates are elevated to their predefined maximum value immediately after the first data assimilation analysis is conducted and stays near the maximum value during the rest of period every year. mrZI and srDO are consistent from year to year except for the very end of the analysis period, after mid-October. On the other hand, estimated mrZs and CrSi follow different paths every year.

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Figure 4.4.1.1 Time series of selected estimated model parameters (ensemble mean). *grPl*: growth rate of large phytoplankton. *grPs*: growth rate of small phytoplankton. *mrZl*: mortality rate of large zooplankton. *mrZs*: mortality rate of small zooplankton. *srDO*: sinking rate of detritus and opal. *CrSi*: Carbon to Silicate ratio.

To validate the impact of parameter estimation on SEAMLESS indicators, we use the indicators averaged over four of the ARC MFC validation domains (Figure 4.4.1.2), Iceland Basin and Irminger Basin (IBIB) domain, the Norwegian (NRW) domain, the Greenland Sea (GL) domain and Barents Sea (BR) domain. Note that estimated parameters are global values and impact the entire model domain. The current ARC MFC system is a joint state-parameter estimation system and selected biogeochemical (BGC) parameters are estimated online during the reanalysis production. Under SEAMLESS, we have used the fixed parameter (default) values in table 3.4.1.1.

Figure 4.4.1.2. Definition of ARC MFC validation domains. Short name in each domain is DSBB: Davis Strait and Buffin Bay, IBIB: Iceland Basin and Irminger Basin, NRW: Norwegian Sea, GL Greenland Sea, BR: Barents Sea and KR: Kara Sea.

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Figure 4.4.1.3. Time series of the surface chlorophyll concentration with fixed parameters of SEAMLESS setup (left column) and with joint state-parameter estimation system of CMEMS (ARC MFC) setup (middle column) and model free run (right column) over the Irminger and Iceland Basins (IBIB, 1st row) the Norwegian Sea (NRW, 2nd row), the Greenland Sea (GL, 3rd row) and Barents Sea (BR, 4th row) in 2009. Solid lines are ensemble means and shading is ensemble spread (standard deviation). Blue is for the model and orange is for observation in the left column.

One speculation on the sustained high value of grPI and grPs after parameter estimation (Figure 4.4.1.1) is the latitude and regional dependency of the onset timing of the spring bloom across the ARC MFC domain, that ranges from the northern edge of the North Atlantic subpolar gyre to the Barents Sea (Figure 4.4.1.2). Since timing of the spring bloom onset is late over the entire domain in model free run (Figure 4.4.1.3 right column), grPI and grPs are needed to be kept high to trigger earlier onset of the spring bloom to fix the model bias. In the next version of the ARC MFC BGC reanalysis system, we will fix this issue by using region-dependent parameters set.

4.4.2 The MFC products for the target indicators

In the Norwegian Sea, the onset of the spring bloom in 2009 can be detected as early as mid-April in the satellite chlorophyll concentration data (Figure 4.4.1.3). The Ensemble model free run has a delayed onset about 2 weeks later. After the onset, the peak value of satellite chlorophyll concentration only reaches to about 1 mg/m³, but the free run reaches as high as 2 mg/m³ and the timing of the peak comes about two weeks later than satellite observations. The bloom in the model free run ends at the beginning of July and there is no significant bloom for the rest of the summer towards the fall. This indicates that the BGC-ocean coupled model of the ARC MFC system has a clear

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bias in phytoplankton phenology against satellite observation and a similar feature can be found in the other three domains. The biased timing of the spring bloom onset is corrected in the analysis with parameter estimation (Figure 4.4.1.3 middle panels) and period of the bloom is extended to the first week of August in all domains. However, the timing and strength of the peak remain significantly later and stronger than what satellite observation sees. Without parameter estimation, the timing of the onset is about two weeks later than observations and the duration is also shorter than observation, missing most of the summer and fall bloom. The peak amplitude of the spring bloom in the analysis without parameter estimation (Figure 4.4.1.3 left column) over NRW is about 1.5 mg/m³ and surprisingly closer to the peak amplitude in the observation than the analysis with parameter estimation. The same tendencies can be found in IBIB.

The degradation of the peak amplitude in the analysis with parameter estimation can be attributed to the high maximum phytoplankton growth rate, elevated by parameter estimation (Figure 4.4.1.1 top panels). As soon as the data assimilation cycle starts, both maximum growth rates for large phytoplankton (Diatoms) and small phytoplankton (Flagellates) are pushed to their respective upper limits and the values stay high during most of the assimilation period for the large phytoplankton and up to early June for the small phytoplankton. These elevated growth rates help the coupled model to achieve the early onset of the spring bloom but also produce a too strong bloom at its peak.

The impact of the parameter estimation on the data assimilation analysis becomes clearer after evaluating phytoplankton functional types. In the BGC model ECOSMO, the phytoplankton biomass consists mainly of Ps: small phytoplankton (flagellates) and Pl: large phytoplankton (diatom). In the model free run, both Ps and Pl reach their first peak at the same time around the end of May in the NRW (Figure 4.4.2.1) and at around the first week of June in IBIB. However, observational records suggest that the two phytoplankton types reach their peaks at different timing in NRW (e.g., Dale et al., 1998) and in IBIB (e.g., Lars et al., 2020). Both in NRW and IBIB, the first peak in May to June is explained by a strong bloom of diatoms which decays quickly by July. Following the diatom bloom, the flagellates bloom reaches its peak in June to July and gradually decays during the rest of the bloom period. This feature is missing in the free run but is recovered in both data assimilation settings with and without parameter estimation. The separate timing of bloom peaks between the two phytoplankton types is clearer in the analysis with parameter estimation. Note that the model bias in timing of the spring bloom for the two phytoplankton types is improved in the new version of the ARC MFC BGC model module, ECOSMO II (CHL) (Yumruktepe et al., 2022). With the new module, early onset of the strong diatom bloom and the subsequent weak, but prolonged flagellate bloom which resembles to the data assimilated products in Figure 4.4.2.1 is reproduced in model free run over NRW.

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Figure 4.4.2.1. Time series of the surface phytoplankton functional type composition with fixed parameters of SEAMLESS setup (left column) and with joint state-parameter estimation system of CMEMS (ARC MFC) setup (middle column) and model free run (right column) over the Irminger and Iceland Basins (IBIB) the Norwegian Sea (NRW), the Greenland Sea (GL) and Barents Sea (BR) in 2009. Time series of surface phytoplankton functional composition (right column) over the Norwegian (NRW) domain in 2009. Light green is for diatom (DIA) and dark green for flagellate (FLA) in the right column.

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Figure 4.4.2.2. Time series of the trophic efficiency over the top 200 meter depth with fixed parameters of SEAMLESS setup (left column) and with joint state-parameter estimation system of CMEMS (ARC MFC) setup (left column) over the Irminger and Iceland Basins (IBIB) the Norwegian Sea (NRW), the Greenland Sea (GL) and Barents Sea (BR) in 2009.

4.5 The NWES MFC domain

4.5.1 Validation of the reanalysis

The final SEAMLESS reanalysis was validated by the independent observations provided by the L4 station in the western English Channel. The validation is shown in Fig.4.5.1.1, both for some physics variables (temperature, salinity), and multiple biogeochemistry variables (total surface chlorophyll, oxygen, nitrate, phosphate, silicate and ammonium). The L4 oxygen observations for 2018 were highly anomalous (Skakala et al, 2023) indicating some issue with the data, due to which we display also L4 observations. Fig.4.5.1.1 shows that all the variables validate reasonably against the in situ

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observations with the exception of nitrate and ammonia, showing substantial biases. This indicates bias in how the reanalysis represents nitrogen cycle (e.g. possibly nitrification).

Fig.4.5.1.1: Comparison of the SEAMLESS reanalysis at the L4 station in the western English Channel. Shown are L4 surface observations as well as their seasonal climatology.

4.5.2 The MFC products for the target indicators

The SEAMLESS indicators 2018 reanalyses for NWS domain are shown in Fig.4.5.2.1-4.5.2.2. Fig.4.5.2.1 shows time series of NWES-averaged values of the different indicators, including information on their uncertainty. Phytoplankton bloom (surface chlorophyll and phenology indicators) peaks in late April, with a much less distinctive maxima than in the free model run (Skakala et al, 2022). The most biologically productive areas are near the delta of the Thames river and in the southern North Sea (Fig.4.5.5.2), which is again consistent with previous studies (Skakala et al, 2018, 2020, 2022). The most uncertain indicator is phytoplankton community structure, showing relatively limited temporal (Fig.4.5.2.1) and also spatial variability (Fig.4.5.2.2). The community structure values close to 1 indicate that NWS phytoplankton is dominated by microphytoplankton. POC in the bottom part of the water-column is a proxy for carbon export and shows distinctive seasonality that follows with a characteristic time-delay the phytoplankton bloom. The bottom oxygen seasonality is negatively

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correlated with the bottom POC due to the remineralization of organic matter. The trophic efficiency shows that phytoplankton dominates zooplankton over the bloom period and vice versa during the Winter. It also indicates growth of zooplankton following the phytoplankton bloom.

Fig. 4.5.2.1 The time-series for the NWES averages of the different SEAMLESS target indicators. The black line shows ensemble median, the red colour shading shows the two quantiles around the median value and the orange colour shading the full spread of the ensemble.

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Fig.4.5.2.2. The distributions of SEAMLESS target indicators across the NWS. Shown are mean values for the March-December 2018 period calculated from the ensemble median.

5. Discussion and the final recommendations

	ARC	BAL	GLO/IBI	MED	NWS
System TRL	TRL8	TRL5	TRL4	TRL5	TRL5
Simulation cost	high	high	high	high	High
Phenology	good	good	very good	good	very good
Net primary production	medium	good	good	good	Good

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POC export	n/a	n/a	medium	good	Medium
Trophic efficiency	medium	medium	medium	medium	Medium
Phytoplankt on community structure	good	medium	n/a	good	Poor
Bottom oxygen	n/a	very poor	n/a	n/a	Good
pH	n/a	medium	n/a	n/a	Poor

Tab.5.1. Summary of performance of the final SEAMLESS system configurations across the different MFC domains. The Table shows the total readiness level (TRL), the cost of using the SEAMLESS configuration, qualitatively evaluated on a scale “very high, high, medium, low, very low”, and the quality of the target indicator product evaluated on a scale “very good, good, medium, poor, very poor”.

The Tab.5.1 summarizes the main points based on which the final MFC systems developed in SEAMLESS can be recommended for the CMEMS implementation. It is clear from the Tab.5.1 that operational centres must consider carefully the high computational cost associated with ensemble methods. The high cost of the SEAMLESS systems might play an important role in the MFC decision making, e.g. whether these methods could be used for reanalyses, or real-time forecasting. Measures on how to reduce the problem can be considered, either through investment into HPC, or through cost saving measures, like better adjusting model resolution of its different components, complementing the models with machine learning and further. Analysing such cost-reducing measures is however far beyond the scope of this project.

The final SEAMLESS systems are mostly in a similar stage of development (TRL5: “Technology validated in relevant environment”), which is understandable as they have been both developed and validated in SEAMLESS, but not yet fully implemented by the MFCs. Any further progress in terms of TRLs relies on direct involvement of MFCs to test and implement these systems as part of their operations. In this sense the systems are as ready as they can currently be.

When it comes to SEAMLESS target indicator products which are either new versions of existing CMEMS indicators (e.g. community structure, oxygen, net primary production), or entirely new indicators (e.g. POC), their quality has also been assessed in Tab.5.1. The Table suggests that the SEAMLESS products for the most typically controlled target indicators, such as phenology, or net primary production are consistently of very high quality across all of the MFCs. Other quantities, such as POC and trophic efficiency have slightly reduced quality but can be still recommended. The quality of the remaining three indicators (community structure, pH and bottom oxygen) is more variable and dependent on the MFC domain. We would like to highlight that the quality of the indicators was dominantly measured here by the ensemble-informed uncertainty. It would be highly desirable to get more investment into observations of the SEAMLESS indicators. These observations would enable MFCs to evaluate also the model bias and more directly validate the indicator uncertainty represented

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by the ensemble (e.g. using rank histograms, or reliability metrics). Apart from a couple of indicators, such observations of the SEAMLESS indicators are so far very rare.

Some of the SEAMLESS developments have been already implemented by MFCs, or can be easily implemented by MFCs in the future. For example, the optimization of the bio-optical parameters with 1D GOTM-FABM-BFM and PARSAC calibration tool has been up-taken by the analysis and forecast CMEMS MED MFC system for the November 2023 entry service. Furthermore, on the BAL domain the development of dynamical ensembles is a major advance and is based on a fully compatible code with the BAL MFC (including using PDAF and a joint code-base). This will allow the BAL MFC to uptake easily the developments performed in SEAMLESS. In addition, the coupling code between NEMO and PDAF is available as free open-source code on Github (<https://github.com/PDAF/NEMO-PDAF>). This allows other users (from operations and from research) to develop ensemble-based data assimilation systems for their region.

Finally, although SEAMLESS represents a substantial advancement in MFC ensemble capacity and its ability to address timely problems such as multi-platform data assimilation (DA) and coupled physical-biogeochemical data assimilation, more future work will be needed to fully utilize the potential of these developments. Here, we will highlight a few issues that still remain open: (i) despite major advancements in the tools for coupled physical-biogeochemical DA, their potential was not always realized. For example, on the NWS the problem of coupled DA remains largely unsolved, and we suspect that the development of fully multi-variate DA based on the ensembles could represent a major advance in the future. (ii) The ensembles should be gradually improved by including new sources of uncertainty not represented in SEAMLESS. Furthermore, we recommend to utilize the multi-model approach adopted by SEAMLESS (also via FABM) to estimate the hard-to-evaluate model structural uncertainties via multi-model ensembles. (iii) SEAMLESS has in multiple cases improved MFC parametrizations. It has however been also observed that the parameter values across the spatial and temporal domains show very high variability. This suggests that implementing spatio-temporally variable parametrizations in the MFC models might be a highly desirable route to take. Similarly, wherever it does not exist, it might be highly desirable to introduce joint state-parameter estimation in the MFC systems, allowing for spatially variable parameter estimation. SEAMLESS has provided essential information for such developments (via parameter sensitivity ranking) and tools to test these developments in 1D.

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